

Enabling access to weather, climate and oceanographic data across institutions

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For a summary of this report see the [Synthesis](#) (prepared 14/09/2023).

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Introduction

In Australia, research in the atmospheric, oceanographic and climate sciences is conducted by many organisations, including federal and state government agencies (e.g., CSIRO, the Australian Bureau of Meteorology, the New South Wales Department of Planning and Environment), universities and, in some cases, private companies, and provided with computational support by others (e.g., NCI, the Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre). One obstacle to the efficient conduct of this research is the sharing of data between institutions. This report contributes to overcoming this obstacle.

The aims of this report are to:

- 1) Foster collaborations that will facilitate access to weather, climate and oceanographic data for anyone in the Australian research community, regardless of their institution.
- 2) Identify and socialise solutions to data sharing problems that have already been developed.
- 3) Make recommendations on next steps to address those that have not been solved.

The report draws on learnings from specific initiatives, both in Australia and overseas, to comment on overall data management strategies that can be adopted to improve data accessibility for researchers. The scope of the report includes both governance and technical issues related to data management, data licensing and administrative obstacles in accessing data and sharing data between institutions. The focus is on the research community and the data they use. The provision of data for the purposes of informing decision makers (e.g., in context of weather forecasting and climate services) is out of scope.

Ten case studies were gathered from initiatives that have tackled, or are tackling, issues involving sharing data across institutions (see Table 1). The contributors were asked to provide details of their project, the data challenges they faced, and how they have tackled, or plan to tackle, those challenges. From these case studies, common issues emerged and a range of solutions for each were identified. This report aims to synthesise those findings and presents recommendations on how to address outstanding issues.

The recommendations are designed to initiate discussion among data and infrastructure providers on how they can improve access to data, along with researchers. Many of the recommendations require collaboration across the research and provider communities, and the hope is this will build a shared sense of purpose to unlock the potential in the data for Australian climate research.

Table 1 - Case studies informing this report

Case study	Description
Federated Climate Data Initiative (FCDI)	Project to improve management of high resolution future climate projections data
Copernicus Data Store (Copernicus)	Europe-based service for providing climate data
Australian Climate Service (ACS)	Research and knowledge brokerage project
CSIRO Data Access Portal (CSIRO DAP)	Portal to archive and provide access to research data and software
Integrated Marine Observing System (IMOS)	Service that acquires,curates and distributes marine data
National Environmental Science Program Climate Systems Hub (NESP2)	Research and knowledge brokerage project
National Computational Infrastructure (NCI)	Provider of high-performance computing services
Australian Gridded Climate Data (AGCD)	Bureau of Meteorology operational dataset
Bureau of Meteorology Information Technology Science Section (BoM)	Bureau of Meteorology team responsible for the research, development, and delivery of environmental prediction systems and data science capabilities.
Pawsey Supercomputing Research Centre (Pawsey)	Provider of high-performance computing services

Aspects of enabling data access across institutions

Analysis of the case studies highlighted numerous aspects of enabling data access across institutions (Table 2 and below). These were usually highlighted by several, but not all, case studies. In many cases aspects were highly interrelated, but for the purposes of tractability we discuss them in separate subsections below. Each subsection describes challenges, solutions and recommendations related to an aspect. Relevant case studies for particular points are noted in square brackets (e.g., [Copernicus]).

Table 2 - Aspects of enabling data access across institutions

Aspect	Case studies with most relevant content
Data discoverability	IMOS, CSIRO DAP, NCI, Copernicus, ACS, NESP2, FCDI, Pawsey, AGCD, BoM
Data standards	NCI, Pawsey, CSIRO DAP, IMOS, NCI, ACS, Copernicus, FCDI
Human resources and automation	Copernicus, IMOS, NCI, CSIRO DAP, Pawsey, FCDI, NESP2, AGCD
Data complexity	IMOS, Copernicus, NCI, FCDI, Pawsey, CSIRO DAP, NESP
Data storage	FCDI, Pawsey, Copernicus, CSIRO DAP, AGCD
Speed of data access	FCDI, Copernicus, IMOS, CSIRO DAP, Pawsey, NCI
Location of data	FCDI, NCI, Pawsey, ACS, AGCD
Tracking data usage	NCI, FCDI, CSIRO DAP, NESP2, ACS
Data security	NCI, FCDI, BoM, CSIRO DAP
Data provenance, versioning and currency	AGCD, ACS

Data discoverability

Data discoverability was the number one issue mentioned by the respondents to our AMOS 2020 survey (~80). And the main reason for setting up a working group to develop a [Climate Data Portal](#) that could act as a single source of information on climate data (and other services) available in Australia.

ARDC manages Research Data Australia which lists metadata records for datasets and other research related resources. As the first and most comprehensive initiative of this kind RDA has been instrumental on increasing data discoverability, with IMOS, CSIRO DAP and NCI records automatically ingested into RDA. Enabling this cross-reference to happen is at the core of their operation to improve discoverability. CSIRO DAP previously used the [OAI PMH](#) schema to facilitate this and are now looking at [schema.org](#) to make it easier to import records published on other platforms like Zenodo and Figshare, which are popular with researchers, to make sure they capture data assets from a broad range of CSIRO's research areas.

While making sure climate research products are captured in at least one catalogue, and potentially more than one, is a good start to ensure discoverability, there are still challenges in providing a querying system which is easy, intuitive and effective in discovering data. Comparing the IMOS and CDS [Copernicus] portal, discipline based portals with a high level of control on the metadata records input, and the RDA portal, that needs to accommodate a lot of disciplines, highlights these challenges. In the first, the portal administrator can set *a priori* a set of keywords and use a consistent strategy to apply them to the records. In the second, users provide keywords either based on vocabularies (usually ANZSRC Field of Research) and/or custom made ones. This means that keywords are applied in a non-uniform way, and consequently using them for queries can produce poor results.

If time-poor researchers are not instructed on how to create good metadata records, the discoverability of their research products can be very low.

The fact itself that the data is spread across several catalogues and that even where a mandate exists for researchers to use a specific portal they use other options [CSIRO DAP], is an obstacle to true discoverability. This is highlighted in the two user cases from projects that rely on other organisations' services. Data discoverability is mentioned as an important and unresolved issue by projects like NESP2 and ACS that need to access a variety of data in different formats and available from different sites.

For the data they themselves curate, the ACS is planning to focus on provenance and have well curated public information but there is currently no portal for data discovery, so they depend on other services.

Several respondents mentioned APIs [Pawsey, FCDI, IMOS, AGCD] and cloud environments [NCI, FCDI, Pawsey] as a potential solution to improve discoverability. Noticeably, for Pawsey providing data services is out of scope, but they point out that their new object storage strategy will be metadata-rich and will allow communities to create APIs that can exploit this. The two BoM use cases [BoM, AGCD] highlight a different challenge for discoverability: BoM has a

protocol to ensure data is available and easily accessible to the wider community, this works well for smaller amounts of data, but the discoverability of research data is not as developed, more issues are expected as future projected data volumes are huge.

NCI has created cloud environments where the data can be accessed in place via a global file system. This shares some of the HPC advantages, such as scalable memory and CPUs. NCI is also looking into data indexing and to use metadata to query at sub-dataset scale. However, currently there is still a gap between the official data on the portal and the analysis services, also there is a lot of data which is not listed in the official catalogue or with poorly described catalogue entries. For the first NCI is introducing intake catalogues for all their collections. A number of intake catalogues for climate data at NCI already exist but they were born out of community effort.

Recommendations:

- 1. Avoid catalogue proliferation! Utilise a common catalogue where possible (e.g., oneclimate, ARDC, data.gov.au).*
- 2. Data service providers should use recognised metadata schemas (e.g. schema.org), permitting cross-institutional record harvesting so that catalogues can contain reference to data outside of the local system.*
- 3. Catalogue search design needs to be established based on community/stakeholder use cases.*
- 4. Catalogue search should be based on community vocabularies where such exist.*

Data standards

Ideally we need to have more robust standards, and more investment in data expertise so the standards can be applied.

Making data Open is easy, making it truly FAIR is hard. Publishing files is not technically difficult, however “open” data is of little value if it can’t be found (need for public searchable catalogues supporting persistent identifiers and metadata standards), accessed (downloaded or interacted with remotely), and if it is not interoperable (works with a diverse range of tools and other data by using well described data formats and standards with controlled vocabularies) and reusable (clear open licence and provenance information is available). FAIR data relies on high levels of metadata description and standards compliance, which in turn relies on expertise to implement. If data is well described it will be easier to provide better data indexing [NCI, Pawsey], APIs and other online services.

We need to encourage the use of

- metadata standards, of which there are many (schema.org, RIF-CS, ANSLIC, ISO-19115-3) [CSIRO DAP, Copernicus],
- data standards supporting diverse data types [CSIRO DAP, Copernicus],
- APIs, including metadata harvesting between portals [Pawsey, CSIRO DAP]
- data tools and services.

The (meta)data standards can be enabled/improved with a formal data review process, akin to publication review - Copernicus pair this with enforcing metadata standards on incoming data by CDS data curators - that is, there is a role for the “expert data curator”, it cannot be entirely automated. We can develop tools that scan for compliance with standards like CF and ACDD [NCI], however at the end of the day, every dataset should be critically reviewed with an expert eye to look for potential problems or inconsistencies. This is one of the first steps taken by IMOS, as they created their own augmented version of the CF conventions for data based on different instrumentation.

One approach to data sharing is to make data available through high-availability nodes [FCDI], this is best enabled through data adhering to expected standards, formats and structures (e.g. a data reference syntax), which allows users to move easily between systems [Pawsey]. Use of a common data model and application of CF conventions [Copernicus] with ad hoc extension to support more diverse data (including observations) may support data interoperability [IMOS, NCI, ACS].

Recommendations:

5. *Data conventions, controlled vocabularies, and metadata standards should be applied across all published/shared datasets.*
6. *Datasets should be formally reviewed on submission prior to publication by a specialist data curator or similar data expert.*
7. *A common data model should be used where possible.*
8. *Data should use open source formats, be licenced such that it is open, catalogued, and provided via appropriate data services/APIs/protocols. A procedure should be in place for data retraction and revision, and giving consideration to ethical considerations like the CARE principles.*

Human resources and automation

Although automated facilities such as APIs can help in making large, complex and diverse datasets shareable across institutions [Pawsey, FCDI], enabling use of such data by a wide variety of technical expertise levels requires dedicated human resources at the data repository or service facility. Suitably skilled personnel are required for key tasks, including:

- Supporting data quality and metadata standards to ensure that data are sufficiently reliable, well-described and interoperable. Data providers generally need assistance in this area and standards will not be upheld if this is not available (e.g., IMOS and Copernicus have a very similar approach and that is dependent on data managers' expertise). Note that the increased use of climate data by government and the private sector is increasing the need for rigour in this area [Copernicus, IMOS].
- Administering data review and publication procedures [Copernicus].
- Staffing helpdesks, which help to maximise the usage of data [Copernicus, NCI, CSIRO DAP].

Dedicated data curators are required to perform these tasks. Recruiting personnel with the right combination of technical and computing skills and domain-specific field knowledge remains a challenge [Copernicus, NCI, IMOS].

In an environment where access to suitably skilled personnel is constrained, data stewardship communities of practice [CSIRO DAP] can help to make sure that relevant expertise is shared and that maximum use is made of available human resources. These can particularly help data custodians keep pace with relevant technological advances [NCI], navigate (often lengthy) institutional procedures to licence data [NCI, Copernicus] and maintain awareness of the suitability of different datasets for meeting different use cases [NESP2, AGCD].

Recommendations:

- 9. APIs to enable data access and subsetting should be provided, including self-documenting features to aid provenance.*
- 10. User access to data should be relatively intuitive and well provisioned (e.g., NCI ARE).*
- 11. Support processes should be put in place for data service providers to work with data custodians to ensure data meets required standards.*
- 12. Specialised data curators should provide support for datasets both to users and contributors.*
- 13. Community engagement and constant review and upskilling/refresh is required to ensure data and systems continue to be fit for purpose.*

Data complexity

Data complexity has been mentioned by different groups as a challenge [IMOS, Copernicus, NCI, FCDI, Pawsey and CSIRO DAP], due to a variety of data formats and different ways of organising data.

On the issue of data formats, a binary format called netCDF is commonly used for gridded climate model output and is occasionally seen as a panacea for formatting climate data. However, while there are established standards and conventions for netCDF (the CF conventions), these allow a large range of interpretations and don't cover all file aspects. Notably there are no agreed controlled vocabularies for variable names. In addition, while well-suited to gridded climate model output, it is less suited to handle observations and forecast data.

The challenge of data organisation is different for different groups. For groups for which climate data is not the core business (e.g., NCI, CSIRO DAP, Pawsey), the way climate data is organised is partially or completely left to the data contributor. For example, NCI requires observance of conventions but doesn't try to organise the data further. Pawsey is moving to object storage and rich metadata workflows. While this provides an opportunity for data providers to augment file metadata, as Pawsey doesn't have a data portal, there are no standards imposed. CSIRO DAP can currently only accept the data as it is and leaves the data organisation entirely to the contributors. An upcoming move to S3-based storage will permit greater flexibility to support large data collections, thereby enabling more climate data to be stored in the DAP system itself, where metadata standards may be applied.

Groups running specialised climate data portals, on the other hand, have an imperative to address the complexity of climate datasets and impose standards on them. For example, the Copernicus CDS requires compliance to conventions, has developed a common data model and uses experts to develop workflow to ingest the data provided into this common model. This allows Copernicus to have API-based services to retrieve and analyse data efficiently. FCDI has a similar model - although their data is currently more uniform (output from dynamic downscaling climate model simulations), the distributed nature of it requires a common model to facilitate retrieval and analysis in situ. IMOS has created their own interpretation of netCDF CF conventions for each different kind of ocean observation data they deal with. Similar to Copernicus, expert data managers are used to create ingest workflows.

Organisations like NESP, IMOS, FCDI and Copernicus that deal with audiences with different levels of technical expertise (e.g., a variety of different researchers and sometimes other stakeholders) have an extra challenge to provide data in different formats, while minimising duplication.

Recommendations:

14. Where it is viable to implement field-specific standards and vocabularies, this should be done.

15. Data providers should take into account different end-user needs when choosing data format and services to implement.

Data storage

Although data storage was less of an issue than initially anticipated by the authorship team, the case studies did reveal some storage issues:

- Large data volumes are a challenge to manage [FCDI, Pawsey, Copernicus]. NCI provides one centralised solution used by much of the Australian climate data community to store large amounts of climate data. However, recently, the FCDI has leveraged distributed data nodes to store data.
- Wasteful duplication of data. Copernicus' Common Data Model is an attempt to avoid duplication of data.
- Long-term archiving of data [FCDI, NESP2, CSIRO DAP], including lack of funding for storage and data management support for this [FCDI, NCI]. Some initiatives, such as NESP2 and AGCD, have attempted to overcome this by using existing public data portals that are expected to endure. An alternative approach is to draw in funding from a community of users, on the assumption that maintenance is more likely to be sustainable if multiple initiatives and/or organisations are involved.

Note that in some cases where storage appears to be an issue (e.g., a temporary shortage of disk capacity for NCI's CMIP6 collection), the fundamental issue is a lack of management procedures, including retirement policy around data, some of which may become obsolete relatively quickly and some which may be of permanent value.

Recommendations:

16. Institutions should perform regular audits of data holdings and make updated data catalogues visible to other institutions so that duplicates can be identified.

17. Funding for data coordination, curators and storage should be recognised as an ongoing investment.

- a. *Initiatives generating data should plan for storage provision and archiving of data, being mindful of the potential for both increases and decreases in required capacity over time.*

18. Having shared guidelines on how to manage the entire data lifecycle would help using storage more effectively and consistently across institutions.

Speed of data access

Accessing data from, or contributing data to, very large data volumes can be very slow [FCDI, Copernicus]. Most use cases involve accessing only a small subset of these data volumes, and this allows this challenge to be addressed in several ways:

- Data caches can be “smart”. Firstly, cache-management software can be set up to learn which data are most frequently accessed and retain these on quick-access disk systems, rather than slower-access tape systems [Copernicus]. Secondly, data on disk can be stored in formats, such as `xarray` “hypercubes”, which are easy to query and extract subsets of data from [Copernicus]. In Australia, IMOS is investigating smart subsetting for its Open Access to Ocean Data (AODN) portal and Pawsey and CSIRO DAP are investigating faster cloud-based storage access.
- Processing capacity can be provided for users “close to” (i.e., linked via fast connection to) the data volumes in question. This solution relies on an assumption that most user operations result in an output dataset that is smaller than the input dataset. Instead of the large input dataset being transferred to storage and processing close to the user, the smaller output data are generated close to the input data and are then transferred to the user (i.e., take the compute to the data then retrieve the output). One model for this is NCI, where processing on physical machines, such as Gadi, is available for many research users close to the NCI datasets. Providing processing close to data that is distributed across multiple data storage nodes is more complex, but Virtual Machines (e.g., in the Nectar cloud or in commercial cloud services) [FCDI] may provide a solution in this case.
- Pawsey’s introduction of block storage (S3) buckets gives the community options to create their own Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) to exploit the associated rich metadata and speed up access to it. The tape system also has an S3 gateway that makes retrieval times much faster.

These solutions notwithstanding, there may be a need to upgrade elements of the physical network between key data nodes. For example, the need for a faster network connection between Pawsey and NCI to allow live data processing across HPCs has been identified. In the

case of data that is distributed across multiple data storage nodes, the need for costly network upgrades could be mitigated by ensuring that the most frequently accessed data are located at the best connected nodes [FCDI].

Recommendations:

19. Data service providers should provide data in a way that it can be accessed and subsetting in optimised ways, making use of cloud-ready formats and access/conversion/subsetting libraries.

20. Implement compute resources close to data services to minimise the need for data transfer between institutions, while supporting data to be remotely accessed so that datasets can be brought together from multiple institutions in a single compute environment (with some reduction in data speed).

Location of data

There are many issues related to where data is stored, both from the technical aspects of publishing the data, as well as the data consumer experience of accessing the data. For example, the FCDI has been addressing challenges related to just one data type, CORDEX regional climate data, being distributed across 9 data nodes. These challenges relate to differing levels of accessibility and security across nodes. To a large extent consumers would have no preference on where data are actually stored if they were able to seamlessly find and access them from wherever they do their research. Users are more interested in usability than technical implementation of data storage or location, particularly if tools are available to minimise their perceived need to download/copy the data.

The choice of location where data is stored should be guided by:

- Where was the data produced/captured?
- Noting the large volumes of climate model outputs generated on HPCs, can it be easily moved around and appended? [NCI, Pawsey]
- Where can data be most efficiently managed /governed? Note that if data is in the same location as similar data, it's easier to provide consistent access, formats, etc. and leverage tools that facilitate management and discoverability
- Can the user access the data from where they are doing their work using, for example, services such as APIs and remote access via THREDDS or S3?
- What is the cost of data storage at various locations?
- Do security, licensing and/or copyright issues restrict where the data can be stored? [NCI, FCDI]

There are pros and cons of both the centralised and distributed models for data storage.

Consumers of data have a range of requirements for how they want to access data. Historically, having the data co-located with computation resources at a central location was necessary and enabled much faster processing, and this is still true in some cases, such as accessing inputs to climate model simulations, or intensive pre-processing of CMIP data. Centralised data can also simplify access to multiple data sources if consistent formatting and standards are used across the entire collection. In Australia, NCI provides a large storage facility for many high-profile climate datasets, including CMIP, ERA5, and AGCD. This means that it is often used as a central location for data, not least because it is convenient to store additional data on the NCI for processing alongside those datasets [ACS].

However, the centralised storage model can preclude access to researchers using other infrastructure. For example, not everyone has access to compute allocations at NCI (e.g., data users from outside traditional academic or other large research institutions). Some users may prefer to work in a commercial cloud, or may be contractually obliged to store contributing data in-house, as is often the case for climate projections developed by state governments [FCDI]. Centralising data storage can also create data management and financial overheads, such as large data transfers and the need to maintain multiple data versions [AGCD]. Additionally, in Australia, the use of NCI as a climate data repository has some disadvantages. NCI is not a specialised climate data repository - it serves the entire Australian research community and has to manage its finite resources across different research fields. Hence, only some climate data can be accepted for storage and/or publication at NCI. This can lead to data being scattered across services and repositories.

Standards and well-documented data services (e.g., APIs) can reproduce many of the advantages of the centralised model in a distributed/federated model. The initial cost can be large, but so is the payoff in structuring and documenting data well, and enabling access to an even broader range of data sources. If data is stored in the cloud in high performance (self-described, open) formats and made available through standard APIs, then the ultimate location of the data becomes irrelevant, so long as sufficient network speed exists to pull the subsets of data to the compute when needed following subsetting and filtering using “lazy loading”. Unfortunately, while this approach greatly enhances data accessibility for cloud-based and desktop users, most HPCs, including NCI, block internet connections and so cannot access S3 buckets or THREDDS URLs from their compute nodes.

There is not a one-size fits all solution to data location. In Australia, we are dealing with the interplay between working with ad hoc data creation, and how we might design an ideal climate data “network”.

Recommendations:

- 21. If an accredited specialist host exists for a particular data type, that should be leveraged (e.g., IMOS), however when no clear preference for data host exists, data should be colocated with similar data if possible (e.g., at NCI).*

22. Published data should be made available via cloud/web protocols regardless of location.

Tracking data usage

Only NCI and FCDI mentioned the challenge of tracking data usage. NCI mostly in terms of developing an attribution model to help data providers measure value and impact across their products as they are (re)used.

This implies a way to track usage via DOI, keeping track of citation for data as it already happens for papers. Examples of these are available on the Zenodo platform that has a beta service to show citations of a record on its landing page. CSIRO DAP mentioned the use of altmetrics to measure impact of published datasets.

FCDI is using the Eratos platform and they are developing a dataset usage tracking system as part of a metering service. Data contributors will also have access to this information to measure impact.

Another advantage of tracking data usage that was not mentioned in the use cases, is the ability to do an effective cost/benefit analysis of storing and distributing a dataset, or part thereof. This is particularly relevant when hosting replicated data, that is, when managing reference collections [NESP2, ACS]. Object storage and online access to data both allow administrators to get some statistics on data usage, as they are based on databases. However, without an established interface a data provider would have to put in a specific request to the system administrator to get access to this information. Again, Zenodo provides an example of this form of tracking as it provides the number of total and unique views, and the number of downloads for each of its records.

CSIRO have implemented the “Starfish” tool to track storage contents and frequency of access on their cloud storage system (pre-publication data). The CSIRO DAP web back end permits analysis of frequently searched, accessed and downloaded published data, and in the process generates “recommender” links so that users are given suggestions of relevant datasets based on what other users have searched and used that also accessed this dataset.

Recommendations:

23. A variety of metrics to monitor data access should be implemented by the data provider, to optimise access to commonly used data, and to identify archiving/slower access infrastructure candidates.

24. Data citation metrics may be included in webpages etc to show data usage and impact.

25. Data usage must be tracked to ensure good long-term storage management and safe dataset retirement.

Data security

Data security has been mentioned as a significant issue faced by NCI, FCDI and BoM. Data security pertains to a number of issues:

- Data cannot be modified on the server, it is authoritative (this includes no ability for malicious database modification).
- Data cannot be accessed by anyone unless it is published or actively shared openly.
- Access to sensitive, private, or otherwise restricted data, can be managed by the system to prevent unauthorised access, and new users can be granted access or removed as needed.
- Authorised users have secure communication channels to the data to either interact with the data remotely, or transfer it securely without risk of “man in the middle” attacks.
- Access to sensitive data is managed via explicit authorisation (e.g. Oauth2, SAML), and not “security via obscurity” or simple data server access protection.
- Data serving systems should be not only secure but robust - high levels of up-time and failover capability. Automated/cloud deployments help here.

CSIRO have attempted to resolve these using flexible access permissions and common authorisation via AAF. Other authentication options exist like system-specific credentials [CSIRO DAP, NCI], but the broader AAF permits a wider range of collaborators. The FCDI has placed a data node behind a firewall and access is managed via a sign-up process.

Recommendations:

- 26. Data service providers should be cognisant of cybersecurity considerations and solutions so that data maintains its open access without risk to the host or user.*
- 27. Authorisation to access data when required should use common authentication mechanisms.*
- 28. Published data should have high availability outside of the 9-5 local time window as it may be consumed by anyone anywhere. Systems should be designed to be resilient to maintenance outages and node failures.*

Data provenance, versioning and currency

The main issues around data provenance are ensuring information about how data were generated and/or processed are recorded by the data creators. It is important that this

information is kept with the data so users are clear on the provenance of the data. A related issue is around versioning of data, where data provenance helps users understand the source of data and, where relevant, data currency. Some key datasets are largely static (i.e., once created, they do not change) while others change over time, either via formal version changes or routine updates (e.g., appending recent data to an observational dataset). Updates to operational datasets may take place as frequently as daily. Examples of this are the AGCD daily products, with daily updates which incorporate new data for the most recent day, but on occasions also involve re-runs of outputs for earlier days (e.g. to incorporate station data not received in real time). This may lead to version control issues. Users need to be aware of issues around data version, currency, update frequency, etc. through data catalogues and metadata. It is important to publish data with Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for citation and FAIR data enablement, however DOIs are not really fit for purpose for continuously updating data and other solutions may be needed. This may change in the future if dynamic DOIs can be used.

For capturing data provenance information, essentially data providers need to produce complete metadata that includes details of how data were generated, the methods and tools used, who created it and when, and versioning information.

To ensure users are informed as to the provenance of any data they access, most effective solutions involve keeping the provenance information as close to the data as possible. Metadata records should record the provenance of the data and links to supporting information on how to use the data, and data files can include a link to the official metadata record. Ideally, where possible, the data files themselves should include the provenance metadata. In the case of NetCDF files the metadata within the files can record a record of commands executed to generate the file. In other cases, an archive can include a metadata record as well as the data file (a tar or zip archive containing both). ACS has taken the additional step of storing code and data directories side-by-side so users can access the code used in generating or post-processing data.

Some widely used datasets have been known to have versions proliferated amongst different researchers, meaning the provenance of the data can be lost or become out-of-date. This can lead to the continued use of incomplete, superseded or erroneous data. The efforts to develop reference climate data collections that are kept up-to-date and well documented will alleviate this issue to a large extent as long as users access data from those collections.

Recommendations:

29. Metadata standards need to capture details of data provenance.

30. Ensure that relevant information about the currency of data sets (e.g. whether the data set is static or updated, if it is updated the date of the most recent update and the expected frequency of updates, and the extent, if any, to which updates affect past data) is included in data catalogues and metadata.

31. *Provenance information (or a link to it) should be stored within or with the data itself.*
32. *Store data and the code used to generate or process it side-by-side.*
33. *Curation, promotion and use of reference data collections for widely-used datasets to reduce proliferation of multiple versions of datasets.*